

REGIONAL DISPARITIES IN WOMEN EMPOWERMENT IN INDIA: A MULTI-DIMENSIONAL ANALYSIS BASED ON NATIONAL FAMILY HEALTH SURVEY-5

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Abstract: This study examines regional variations in women's empowerment across different states and union territories (UTs) in India, using data from National Family Health Survey-5 (NFHS-5). Drawing on a multidimensional approach, the index of women empowerment has been constructed using sixteen indicators under six major domains. The study initially reveals that the southern and western regions of India such as Goa, Tamil Nadu, Puducherry, Dadra & Nagar Haveli and Daman & Diu (and also Sikkim in the north-east) achieved high levels of women empowerment. The study further reveals that low levels of women empowerment are not only prevalent in the traditionally recognized 'BIMARU' states (Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, and Uttar Pradesh) but also extend to regions such as West Bengal, Haryana, and Maharashtra (Kumar and Mondal, 2024). A notable contrast is that the study reveals that Kerala, which often holds the top position in the incidence of literacy, is not among the top-performing states and falls within the category of low level of women empowerment. The study suggests that region-specific government interventions should be applied to enhance the level of women empowerment across different regions of the country, with a greater emphasis on improving their decision-making capabilities and economic participation. A correlation matrix has been constructed to evaluate the relationships among the selected variables.

Keywords: Livelihoods, Women empowerment, Regional disparities, Sustainable Development Goals, National Family Health Survey-5

1. Introduction

For generations, patriarchal norms have dictated gender roles in India, shaping expectations for both men and women (Kabeer, 2000). Women's financial and social dependence on men has often restricted their decision-making authority, reinforcing systemic inequalities. As a result, many women struggle to achieve autonomy in both personal and professional spheres despite playing an essential role in shaping families, communities, and economies. Gender discrimination, restricted opportunities, and societal constraints continue to limit their potential. Barriers such as limited

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access to education, employment, and mobility not only hinder their independence but also affect their overall well-being, including reproductive health (Singh et al., 2018). To address gender discrimination-based issues and uplift the lives of women, it is essential to understand the concept and level of women empowerment and the factors affecting it.

Women's empowerment is a dynamic concept with multiple interpretations. To track gender disparities, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) introduced the Gender Development Index (GDI) and the Gender Empowerment Index (GEI) in 1995. The GDI measures gender-based differences in health, education, and economic participation, while the GEI evaluates women's representation in leadership and decision-making roles (Muyoyeta, 2007). The United Nations Development Fund for Women (UNIFEM) describes it as gaining control over resources to secure sustainable livelihoods. Scholars such as Bayeh (2016), Malik (2021), and Kaviarasu and Xavier (2016) emphasize that true empowerment enables women to make informed choices, foster self-reliance, and build confidence.

In 2010, the Gender Inequality Index (GII) was introduced, incorporating broader measures of women's well-being and vulnerabilities. Similarly, the World Economic Forum (2015) offers insights into disparities in economic participation, political involvement, education, and access to healthcare (Duflo, 2011). Additional sector-specific indices, such as the Women's Empowerment in Agriculture Index (WEAI) (Alkire et al., 2013) and the Women's Empowerment in Nutrition Index (WENI) (Narayanan et al., 2019), highlight specific areas where progress is needed.

Scholars have proposed various frameworks to understand the concept of empowerment. Bloom et al. (2001) and Bhagowalia et al. (2012) highlight four key dimensions: decision-making power, mobility, attitudes toward domestic violence, and economic independence. Others, such as Agarwal (1997) and Eswaran and Malhotra (2011), emphasize autonomy, bargaining power, and income generation. Malhotra et al. (2002) emphasize that defining and measuring empowerment necessitates careful consideration of its evolving nature.

Recognizing these inequalities, the Indian government has launched various programmes to promote women's rights and economic independence. Initiatives such as *Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana*, *Beti Bachao Beti Padhao*, *Swadhar Greh* and *Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana* aim to improve education, financial inclusion, and overall welfare. However, despite these efforts, gender disparities persist, underscoring the need for more effective implementation and awareness (Pradhan, 2020).

India ranks 140th out of 150 nations in the Global Gender Gap Report, with only 62.5% of the gender gap closed (Shettigar and Mishra, 2021). Factors such as declining female workforce participation, underrepresentation in politics and leadership, and literacy rate disparities contribute to this standing. Bridging these gaps requires sustained commitment and action. Policymakers must address the root causes of inequality, ensuring that women have equal access to education, career opportunities, and leadership roles. Creating a society where women can fully participate in decision-making processes is essential for achieving meaningful and lasting empowerment.

While significant research has been conducted on women's empowerment, studies addressing spatial variations in empowerment across Indian states remain limited. To bridge this gap, the present study develops a Composite Women's Empowerment Index (WEI) based on data from NFHS-5, providing a state-wise analysis of women's empowerment and interstate disparities. Additionally, this study investigates the relationships between the identified indicators of empowerment, addressing key questions:

- i. How does women's empowerment vary across Indian states?

- ii. Why are some states more advanced in certain dimensions of empowerment than others?
- iii. How are the indicators of empowerment interrelated?

2. Review of Related Literature

Previous research highlights various dimensions of empowerment. Mishra (2020) compared data from NFHS-3 (2005-06) and NFHS-4 (2015-16), revealing a decline in severe disempowerment nationally but a rise in mild disempowerment among previously empowered women. Singh et al. (2018) studied the relationship between recent empowerment trends and contraceptive use, finding limited improvement despite rising empowerment levels.

Mishra and Banerjee (2022) used NFHS-4 data to calculate a multidimensional disempowerment index, revealing higher levels of disempowerment in states such as Haryana, Uttar Pradesh, and Bihar. Biswas and Banu (2023) constructed an Economic Empowerment Index, noting that rural women outperform urban women in economic empowerment. Similarly, Gupta et al. (2019) applied the Women's Empowerment in Agriculture Index (WEAI) and identified group membership, asset ownership, and agricultural credit decision-making as key drivers of disempowerment.

Lastly, Sharma and Das (2021) proposed an integrated model focusing on economic, social, human, and legal dimensions to enhance women empowerment, particularly in rural areas. These studies highlight the multifaceted nature of empowerment and underscore the need for region-specific strategies to address disparities effectively.

The study complements the current literature by emphasizing two key dimensions. First, it investigates spatial variations in women's empowerment across different Indian states. Second, it examines the root causes of intra-state disparities in women's empowerment, providing valuable insights for developing effective policy solutions.

The paper is structured as follows: The first section provides the historical background of the multifaceted approach to women empowerment. Section second outlines the justification for selecting the indicators utilized in the analysis. Section third depicts the data sources and methodologies applied in the study. Section fourth presents the findings and discusses their implications. Section fifth concludes with key observations and proposes recommendations for future initiatives.

The primary objective of this research study is to construct a comprehensive index of women empowerment using data from the National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5). The study aims to analyze the multi-dimensional aspects of women empowerment by integrating various indicators such as education, employment, decision-making autonomy, access to credit, ownership of assets, and mobility. To ensure the robustness of the index, a correlation matrix will be employed to evaluate the interrelationships between these indicators, identifying their collective and individual contributions to women empowerment. This research seeks to provide a holistic understanding of empowerment levels across regions, highlight disparities, and offer insights for policy interventions that can enhance women's empowerment in India.

3. Conceptual Model of Women Empowerment

The conceptual model of women empowerment (Figure 1) employed in this study is rooted in a multidimensional framework that integrates social, economic, and cultural dimensions. It defines empowerment as enhancing women's ability to make strategic life choices in a context where this ability was previously ignored or denied. Key dimensions considered include economic participation and decision-making autonomy, access to money and credit, educational attainment, and ownership

of assets. These dimensions are operationalized through measurable indicators derived from the NFHS-5 data. The model emphasizes the interconnectivity of these dimensions, positing that empowerment is not a singular achievement but a cumulative process influenced by multiple factors. By employing a theoretical foundation that links these dimensions, the study provides a better understanding of empowerment and its implications for gender equity and sustainable development.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of Women Empowerment

5. Methodology

a. Data

This study is predominantly based on the nationally representative NFHS-5 data conducted in 2019-2021. Under the direction of the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MoHFW), Government of India, the National Family Health Survey (NFHS) is a sizable multi-round survey that provides estimates of various indicators at the national, state/union territory (UT), and district levels. For various NFHS rounds, the International Institute for Population Sciences in Mumbai has been designated the nodal agency, and ICF International in Maryland, USA, has offered technical support. Approximately 7,24,115 women between the ages of 15 and 49 who reside in 28 states, 8 union territories, and 707 districts across India were surveyed to gather information on various aspects of women's empowerment. The framework we have used to assess women's empowerment consists of six dimensions (see Table 1).

b. Selection of Indicators

The roots of women's empowerment are built from a combination of interconnected factors, making its analysis both complex and multifaceted. It cannot be adequately evaluated using a singular metric for any geographic region. Instead, a comprehensive assessment must consider a variety of relevant and practical attributes. To assert the level of women empowerment, the NFHS-5 considers 11 parameters. This study includes those eleven parameters including educational attainment under six major domains. Six key dimensions have been identified to conceptualize women's empowerment: employment status, ownership of assets, education, access to money and credit, decision-making autonomy, and freedom of mobility (Figure 1).

Table 1: Dimensions and Indicators of Women Empowerment

Sl. No.	Dimensions	Indicators	Symbols
1.	Employment status of women	Percentage of women employed in the past 12 months	W ₁
		Percentage earning cash (among those employed in the past 12 months)	W ₂
		Percentage of employed women earning more or about the same as their husband	W ₃
2.	Decision-Making	Control over women’s cash earnings (alone or jointly)	W ₄
		Control over men’s (husband’s) cash earnings (alone or jointly)	W ₅
		Percentage of women making decisions about major household purchases.	W ₆
3.	Ownership of assets by women	Percentage of women owning a house (alone or jointly)	W ₇
		Percentage of women owning a land (alone or jointly)	W ₈
		Percentage of women owning a mobile phone (alone or jointly)	W ₉
4.	Mobility	Percentage of women having freedom of movement	W ₁₀
5.	Access to money and credit	Percentage of women having money that they can decide how to use	W ₁₁
		Percentage of women having a bank or savings account that they themselves use	W ₁₂
		Percentage of women knowing a microcredit programme.	W ₁₃
		Percentage of women who have taken a loan from a microcredit programme	W ₁₄
		Percentage of women who use mobile phones for financial transactions	W ₁₅
6.	Educational Empowerment	Women literacy rate	W ₁₆

Source: Compiled by the author through the report of NFHS-5

To effectively address these dimensions, 16 specific indicators have been selected based on prior research and available data, as shown in Table 1. These indicators offer valuable insights into the status of women’s empowerment across states in a developing country like India. Evaluating individual indicators often fails to provide an integrated or accurate understanding of the larger picture (Mondal et al., 2021). Therefore, constructing a composite Women Empowerment Index that cohesively incorporates multiple indicators becomes crucial. Empowering women has been universally acknowledged as a key contributor to improved demographic outcomes (Dyson and Moore, 1983). However, its broad and sometimes vague definition presents challenges in measurement (Bishop and Bowman, 2014).

Women empowerment can be accessed through various dimensions, including employment opportunities (Brooke, 2006), ownership of assets (Khan et al., 2020), the ability to make decisions (Misra et al., 2021), freedom of mobility (Mehta and Sai, 2021), and personal experiences with domestic or spousal violence (Stöckl et al., 2021). These dimensions shed light on broader issues, such as vulnerabilities in sexual and reproductive health and the ability of women to make decisions about their own lives and futures.

While earlier studies often focused on isolated dimensions, the present study takes a holistic approach, integrating six interconnected dimensions to provide a more comprehensive understanding of women’s empowerment. The identified indicators aim to highlight disparities and progress in women’s empowerment across various states in India.

c. Forming the Dimensions

i. Employment Status of Women

The employment of women is a cornerstone of empowerment, enabling financial independence, enhancing decision-making abilities, and elevating societal standing. It is also a critical contributor to both household stability and the broader economy (Kabeer, 1999). The participation of women in the workforce has evolved significantly over time. Earlier research highlighted low engagement due to socio-cultural restrictions, limited education, and domestic duties. Nevertheless, advancements in education and globalization have gradually opened pathways for women to enter various professional fields, especially in urban and formal settings. It was observed that despite a steady rise in female labor force participation from the 1990s onward, disparities persist across regions (International Labour Organization, 2020).

In this context, particularly in India, the participation of rural women has declined, attributed to higher educational attainment and migration trends, according to data from the National Sample Survey Organization (NSSO) (Chaudhary and Verick, 2014). In contrast, urban women are increasingly employed in professional roles, a shift driven by greater access to education and training opportunities (Desai and Joshi, 2019). Despite progress, significant challenges remain, including underrepresentation in leadership roles and high-paying sectors, highlighting the need to address systemic inequalities and cultural biases in employment.

ii. Decision-Making

Women's decision-making power is essential for fostering gender equality, allowing them to take active roles in shaping household dynamics, contributing to societal progress, and ensuring their voices are heard in critical matters (Kabeer, 1999). Research indicates that employed women are more likely to influence important decisions related to their children's education, family healthcare, and household budgets (UNICEF, 2021). In the Indian context, the (NFHS-5) highlights that working women have greater involvement in family planning and financial matters compared to those who are not employed (Government of India, 2021). Over time, women's decision-making roles have expanded to areas like political participation and asset ownership, indicating shifting social dynamics (ILO, 2020; Chaudhary and Verick, 2014). Government initiatives like the (MGNREGA) have empowered rural women by offering steady income and enhancing their negotiating power in. Furthermore, Desai and Joshi (2019) suggest that higher education equips women with the confidence to take charge of significant issues such as inheritance and career planning. Despite these advancements, gender norms and restricted access to resources continue to pose challenges, emphasizing the need for comprehensive policy reforms (UN Women, 2020).

iii. Ownership of Assets by Women

Ownership of assets by women plays a pivotal role in boosting their economic stability, increasing their influence in household decisions, and improving their social standing (Agarwal, 1994; Deere and Doss, 2006). Research highlights that women with secure property rights tend to have greater control over family finances, investments, and decisions related to their children's future (UN Women, 2020). While legal reforms and programs have gradually expanded asset ownership among women, challenges remain. For example, joint land titles in India have provided women with better access to property and financial resources; however cultural barriers and inconsistent policy enforcement still limit progress (Chowdhry, 2011).

iv. Mobility

Women's mobility is essential for empowerment, enabling them to access education, job opportunities, healthcare, and social networks, which fosters independence and self-reliance (Kabeer, 1999). Historically, societal norms and safety concerns have significantly limited women's ability to move freely (Pande et al., 2017). In recent years, however, urban areas have seen positive shifts, with improved public transport systems and infrastructure making it easier for women to travel (UN Women, 2020). Initiatives such as women-only transport services and safety measures in countries like India have further encouraged independent mobility (Nair et al., 2021). Yet, rural women continue to face challenges due to cultural restrictions and inadequate transport infrastructure, underscoring the need for targeted interventions.

v. Access to Money and Credit

Access to money and credit is a cornerstone of women's economic empowerment, enabling them to start businesses, pursue education, and improve their families' quality of life (Kabeer, 1999). Historically, women have encountered significant obstacles in obtaining financial resources due to discriminatory practices and inadequate property rights (Agarwal, 1994). In recent years, microfinance programs and self-help groups have played a transformative role in bridging this gap, particularly in developing nations (UN Women, 2020). Initiatives like India's Self-Employed Women's Association (SEWA) have provided women with affordable credit options and essential financial literacy, fostering economic independence (Chowdhry, 2011). However, systemic barriers, including a lack of collateral and deep-rooted societal norms, continue to limit equitable financial access for many women (Deere and Doss, 2006).

vi. Educational Attainment

Education is a vital foundation for empowering women, improving their economic opportunities, enhancing their decision-making skills, and enabling upward social mobility (UNESCO, 2021). Over the past two decades, efforts worldwide have significantly expanded women's access to education, with notable increases in primary and secondary school enrollment (UNICEF, 2022). In India, women's literacy rates have improved significantly, rising from 54% in 2001 to 70% in 2021, driven by initiatives such as the "Beti Bachao Beti Padhao programme" and a growing emphasis on educating girls (Government of India, 2022). However, challenges persist, especially in higher education, where socio-cultural barriers and financial limitations frequently hinder women's advancement.

d. Methods

This article investigates regional inequalities in the level of women empowerment using carefully chosen factors. During the initial step of the analysis, a women empowerment index was developed. In the second stage of the study, a correlation matrix was generated to illustrate the interactions between the detected variables. After gathering information on various relevant factors through a thorough literature review, the data were first normalized to make them unitless. Data normalization is required before building any composite index since the feature sets in different types of data differ. As a result, the primary goal of normalization is to provide a consistent scale for various indicators while minimizing variances in value ranges. According to numerous research, scale equivalence leads to a more stable link between datasets (Das et al., 2021). In the literature, indicators have been standardized using various methodologies, including the Dimension Index (DI) and ranking (Basel et al., 2020; Kumari and Raman, 2021). To normalize the indicators in our analysis, we employed the Dimension Index approach, which the UNDP uses to calculate the Human Development Index. The formula for scale equivalence is as follows:

$$DI_{jk} = \frac{(W_{jk} - Min(W_{.....k}))}{(Max(W_{.....k}) - Min(W_{.....k}))}$$

where

$j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ for the states/UTs in India;

$k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ for the indicators of women empowerment;

W_{jk} is the actual value of the indicator;

$Max(W_{.....k})$ denotes the maximum value in a given state of the k th indicator ($k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$) in the entire nation; and

$Min(W_{.....k})$ represents the minimum value of a given state in k th indicator ($k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$) in the entire nation.

The value of DI_{jk} varies from 0 to 1, where a value of 1 implies that the given state is most empowered in that indicator compared to the other states in the country. The reverse is true for a value of 0 (Kumar and Mondal, 2024). After calculating the DI for each indicator, all the indicator-wise values have been compiled for each state to get an aggregate score. Later, the composite score is divided by the number of indicators (here 16 indicators) to get the index value by using the following formula:

$$WEI = \frac{\sum DIW_1 + \sum DIW_2 + \dots + \sum DIW_n}{n}$$

The index value is categorized from 0 to 1; higher values indicate greater empowerment, while lower values indicate less empowerment. Now, the key goal is to categorize different states into groups based on their women empowerment index scores. There are several methods for categorizing a specific range of values into distinct classes, including natural breaks, quintiles, and equal intervals (Kumar and Mondal, 2024). In this study, the equal interval approach is utilized to categorize states into three levels of women empowerment: high, medium, and low.

6. Results and Discussion

This section aims to evaluate the extent of women empowerment by grouping Indian states into three categories—High, Medium, and Low—based on an index calculated using sixteen indicators under six domain dimensions. A correlation matrix has also been constructed to examine the relationship between the selected indicators across various dimensions of women’s empowerment. For the above-mentioned purposes, this section is divided into four sub-parts.

Table 2: State-wise Values of Various Indicators of Women Empowerment

State/Union Territory	W ₁	W ₂	W ₃	W ₄	W ₅	W ₆	W ₇	W ₈	W ₉	W ₁₀	W ₁₁	W ₁₂	W ₁₃	W ₁₄	W ₁₅	W ₁₆
North																
Chandigarh	23.1	100	52.7	85.1	92.5	91.5	30.4	9.0	70.0	72.1	54.0	87.1	23.6	0.7	33.6	78.7
Delhi	22.2	98.1	33.3	95.3	79.8	78	21.9	12.7	73.8	48.8	56.6	72.5	34.2	6.1	36.5	83.7
Haryana	22.0	81.9	42.5	87.8	76.3	78.6	38.6	30.8	50.4	49	57.2	73.6	33.9	4.8	30.5	79.7
Himachal Pradesh	30.1	72.9	19.3	93.3	77.0	81.7	22.4	20.3	79.5	82.1	61.8	83.1	47.7	4.1	18.8	90.7
Jammu & Kashmir	30.3	60.8	38.6	70.5	67.9	69.2	56.6	51.1	75.2	47.3	51.7	84.9	20.6	3.5	28.1	74.3
Ladakh	47.7	69.0	44.9	68.2	68.8	64.4	71.9	63.8	81.2	47.0	58.0	88.4	18.5	2.9	27.2	74.6
Punjab	24.9	89.7	39.7	91.1	84.5	84.0	63.2	27.1	61.2	61.2	57.2	81.6	41.9	7.2	30.1	79.4

Contd...

Table 2 contd...

State/Union Territory	W ₁	W ₂	W ₃	W ₄	W ₅	W ₆	W ₇	W ₈	W ₉	W ₁₀	W ₁₁	W ₁₂	W ₁₃	W ₁₄	W ₁₅	W ₁₆
Rajasthan	30.4	60.1	37.8	80.1	70.6	73.8	26.0	20.7	50.2	36.4	53.1	79.6	42.8	4.1	20.1	64.7
Uttarakhand	25.7	77.8	31.5	92.7	78.8	82.2	23.8	17.5	60.9	55.7	48.6	80.2	50.0	7.6	18.7	79.8
Central																
Chhattisgarh	54.3	82.0	47.6	88.9	83.3	85.8	45.1	38.8	40.7	45.5	57.8	80.3	46.7	6.2	24.3	72.5
Madhya Pradesh	37.6	75.6	43.0	85.0	74.3	75.9	38.9	32.3	38.5	36.2	49.4	74.7	47.9	7.9	23.3	65.4
Uttar Pradesh	20.6	75.4	40.9	85.6	75.2	80.8	51.2	42.7	46.5	34.7	54.5	75.4	38.0	4.5	18.0	66.1
East																
Bihar	19.2	70.7	45.6	91.3	79.5	78.4	54.4	43.8	51.4	43.2	48.5	76.7	59.4	14.3	10.4	55
Jharkhand	26.2	70.2	40.0	88.1	82.7	86.0	63.6	54.6	49.0	48.3	51.9	79.6	61.0	13.5	20.0	61.7
Odisha	27.3	87.9	33.6	91.6	81.0	82.1	42.5	36.6	50.1	30.1	45.4	86.5	74.4	25.3	17.3	69.5
West Bengal	20.9	92.3	39.2	89.1	72.2	80.8	22.0	16.7	50.1	58.3	60.6	76.5	52.0	12.7	12.8	72.9
Northeast																
Arunachal Pradesh	43.1	62.6	47.0	83.1	73.4	81.7	68.7	62.8	76.4	49.1	51.6	78.2	30.3	8.3	38.4	71.3
Assam	21.8	88.5	39.6	87.5	77.7	84.1	42.2	34.8	57.2	34.3	28.7	78.5	62.5	13.6	19.2	75.1
Manipur	53.6	84.7	44.8	84.4	80.6	84.0	57.3	24.8	72.2	31.2	40.0	74.0	49.8	8.2	10.7	85.3
Meghalaya	54.7	86.0	32.4	89.3	80.6	87.3	64.1	44.6	67.5	36.1	49.0	70.4	21.2	6.3	15.8	87.6
Mizoram	34.0	80.7	25.7	95.4	89.6	94.3	19.4	13.9	82.3	75.4	32.7	80.7	13.8	2.1	17.2	94.0
Nagaland	41.2	50.5	42.8	97.4	93.9	97.7	25.5	15.8	82.5	32.6	40.3	63.7	23.4	2.5	19.7	83.4
Sikkim	35.6	89.1	26.4	90.5	77.7	85.0	52.4	39.7	88.6	66.2	67.6	76.4	32.9	9.1	35.1	87.1
Tripura	32.5	74.5	44.3	91.5	76.4	85.2	15.8	10.7	53.1	53.5	55.2	76.9	59.2	21.3	6.9	78.3
West																
Dadra & Nagar Haveli and Daman & Diu	32.6	97.0	59.9	76.7	82.2	83.5	55.8	50.1	60.5	74.2	76.6	83.6	35.0	2.4	22.6	75.6
Goa	30.4	93.1	41.6	99.0	79.8	85.5	22.8	9.2	91.2	23.8	63.9	88.3	75.2	9.9	48.0	92.2
Gujarat	38.2	78.6	53.2	90.5	81.2	81.7	42.2	35.0	48.8	56.2	57.6	70.0	43.2	3.9	21.7	73.4
Maharashtra	43.9	83.4	40.0	85.1	74.1	78.2	21.5	14.7	54.8	48.8	54.4	72.8	51.6	8.3	29.8	82.3
South																
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	22.5	96.6	31.5	100	82.4	85.1	14.5	8.9	80.8	61.6	74.7	89.2	30.9	3.6	13.6	80.5
Andhra Pradesh	49.8	87.7	37.8	78.5	70.9	75.5	45.6	24.5	48.9	42.5	29.4	81.8	61.4	29.7	21.4	66.7
Karnataka	45.8	89.4	36.6	73.9	68.2	73.4	66.2	53.7	61.8	31.6	58.6	88.7	56.9	17.3	43.0	73.4
Kerala	29.0	98.6	32.9	91.0	68.6	81.1	24.5	11.5	86.6	15.0	53.4	78.5	57.5	9.8	22.6	97.4
Lakshadweep	13.0	100	33.5	100	80.0	90.5	29.7	6.1	84.0	2.4	40.3	66.9	45.2	1.4	14.9	95.2
Puducherry	40.5	97.5	40.4	93.9	82.6	87.4	33.6	10	82.8	35.9	49.8	92.6	79.5	10.8	34.2	89.7
Tamil Nadu	46.0	94.8	35.8	87.1	78.3	83.4	47.0	21.9	74.6	39.7	42.6	92.2	73.8	18.2	26.9	84.0
Telangana	53.3	92.8	38.5	75.2	68.7	76.4	63.6	42.6	60.0	39.7	31.8	84.4	62.0	24.1	21.1	64.8

Note: All values are in percentages.

Source: <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/FR375/FR375.pdf>

Table 3: Region-wise Dimension Index Values of the Indicators of Women Empowerment

State/Union Territory	DIW ₁	DIW ₂	DIW ₃	DIW ₄	DIW ₅	DIW ₆	DIW ₇	DIW ₈	DIW ₉	DIW ₁₀	DIW ₁₁	DIW ₁₂	DIW ₁₃	DIW ₁₄	DIW ₁₅	DIW ₁₆	Total	WEI	Stages of Women Empowerment
Tamil Nadu	0.79	0.89	0.41	0.59	0.40	0.57	0.57	0.27	0.69	0.47	0.29	0.99	0.91	0.60	0.49	0.95	9.88	0.62	High Level of Women Empowerment
Dadra & Nagar Haveli and Daman & Diu	0.47	0.94	1.00	0.27	0.55	0.57	0.72	0.76	0.42	0.90	1.00	0.69	0.32	0.06	0.38	0.82	9.87	0.62	High Level of Women Empowerment
Goa	0.42	0.86	0.55	0.97	0.46	0.63	0.14	0.05	1.00	0.27	0.73	0.85	0.93	0.32	1.00	0.68	9.86	0.62	High Level of Women Empowerment
Sikkim	0.54	0.78	0.17	0.70	0.38	0.62	0.66	0.58	0.95	0.80	0.81	0.44	0.29	0.69	1.00	0.70	9.70	0.61	High Level of Women Empowerment
Puducherry	0.66	0.95	0.52	0.81	0.57	0.69	0.33	0.07	0.84	0.42	0.44	1.00	1.00	0.35	0.66	0.23	9.54	0.60	High Level of Women Empowerment
Karnataka	0.79	0.79	0.43	0.18	0.01	0.27	0.90	0.82	0.44	0.37	0.62	0.87	0.66	0.57	0.88	0.43	9.03	0.56	High Level of Women Empowerment
Jharkhand	0.32	0.40	0.51	0.63	0.57	0.65	0.86	0.84	0.20	0.58	0.48	0.55	0.72	0.44	0.32	0.88	8.95	0.56	High Level of Women Empowerment
Chandigarh	0.24	1.00	0.82	0.53	0.95	0.81	0.28	0.05	0.60	0.87	0.53	0.81	0.15	0.00	0.65	0.64	8.93	0.56	High Level of Women Empowerment
Punjab	0.29	0.79	0.50	0.72	0.64	0.59	0.85	0.36	0.43	0.74	0.59	0.62	0.43	0.22	0.56	0.60	8.93	0.56	High Level of Women Empowerment
Chhattisgarh	0.99	0.64	0.70	0.65	0.59	0.64	0.53	0.57	0.04	0.54	0.61	0.57	0.50	0.19	0.42	0.43	8.61	0.54	High Level of Women Empowerment
Arunachal Pradesh	0.72	0.24	0.68	0.47	0.21	0.32	0.94	0.98	0.72	0.59	0.48	0.50	0.25	0.26	0.77	0.28	8.61	0.54	High Level of Women Empowerment
Telangana	0.97	0.85	0.47	0.22	0.03	0.36	0.86	0.63	0.41	0.47	0.06	0.72	0.73	0.81	0.35	0.55	8.49	0.53	Medium Level of Women Empowerment
Odisha	0.34	0.76	0.35	0.74	0.50	0.53	0.49	0.53	0.22	0.35	0.35	0.79	0.92	0.85	0.25	0.49	8.46	0.53	Medium Level of Women Empowerment
Mizoram	0.97	0.69	0.63	0.51	0.49	0.59	0.75	0.32	0.64	0.36	0.24	0.36	0.55	0.26	0.09	0.92	8.37	0.52	Medium Level of Women Empowerment
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	0.23	0.93	0.30	1.00	0.56	0.62	0.00	0.05	0.80	0.74	0.96	0.88	0.26	0.10	0.16	0.76	8.35	0.52	Medium Level of Women Empowerment
Meghalaya	1.00	0.72	0.32	0.66	0.49	0.69	0.86	0.67	0.55	0.42	0.42	0.23	0.11	0.19	0.22	0.67	8.22	0.51	Medium Level of Women Empowerment
Ladakh	0.83	0.37	0.63	0.00	0.03	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.81	0.56	0.61	0.85	0.07	0.08	0.49	0.77	8.10	0.51	Medium Level of Women Empowerment
Gujarat	0.60	0.57	0.83	0.70	0.51	0.52	0.48	0.50	0.20	0.68	0.60	0.22	0.45	0.11	0.36	0.71	8.04	0.50	Medium Level of Women Empowerment
Andhra Pradesh	0.88	0.75	0.46	0.32	0.12	0.33	0.54	0.32	0.20	0.50	0.01	0.63	0.72	1.00	0.35	0.47	7.60	0.48	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Himachal Pradesh	0.41	0.45	0.00	0.79	0.35	0.52	0.14	0.25	0.78	1.00	0.69	0.67	0.52	0.12	0.29	0.42	7.40	0.46	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Bihar	0.15	0.41	0.65	0.73	0.45	0.42	0.70	0.65	0.24	0.51	0.41	0.45	0.69	0.47	0.09	0.38	7.40	0.46	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Delhi	0.22	0.96	0.34	0.85	0.46	0.41	0.13	0.11	0.67	0.58	0.58	0.30	0.31	0.19	0.72	0.34	7.17	0.44	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Maharashtra	0.74	0.66	0.51	0.53	0.24	0.41	0.12	0.15	0.31	0.58	0.54	0.31	0.58	0.26	0.56	0.58	7.08	0.44	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Uttarakhand	0.30	0.55	0.30	0.77	0.42	0.53	0.16	0.20	0.43	0.67	0.42	0.57	0.55	0.24	0.29	0.58	6.98	0.44	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Mizoram	0.50	0.61	0.16	0.86	0.83	0.90	0.09	0.14	0.83	0.92	0.08	0.59	0.00	0.05	0.25	0.16	6.97	0.44	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Tripura	0.47	0.48	0.62	0.73	0.33	0.62	0.02	0.08	0.28	0.64	0.55	0.46	0.69	0.71	0.00	0.26	6.94	0.43	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Nagaland	0.68	0.00	0.58	0.92	1.00	1.00	0.19	0.17	0.83	0.38	0.24	0.00	0.15	0.06	0.31	0.41	6.92	0.43	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Uttar Pradesh	0.18	0.50	0.53	0.55	0.28	0.49	0.64	0.63	0.15	0.41	0.54	0.40	0.37	0.13	0.27	0.84	6.91	0.43	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Kerala	0.38	0.97	0.33	0.72	0.03	0.50	0.17	0.09	0.91	0.16	0.52	0.51	0.67	0.31	0.38	0.25	6.90	0.43	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Assam	0.21	0.77	0.50	0.61	0.38	0.59	0.48	0.50	0.35	0.40	0.00	0.51	0.74	0.44	0.30	0.00	6.78	0.42	Low Level of Women Empowerment
West Bengal	0.19	0.84	0.49	0.66	0.17	0.49	0.13	0.18	0.22	0.70	0.67	0.44	0.58	0.41	0.14	0.46	6.77	0.42	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Haryana	0.22	0.63	0.57	0.62	0.32	0.43	0.42	0.43	0.23	0.58	0.59	0.34	0.31	0.14	0.57	0.23	6.63	0.41	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Jammu & Kashmir	0.41	0.21	0.48	0.07	0.00	0.14	0.73	0.78	0.70	0.56	0.48	0.73	0.10	0.10	0.52	0.58	6.59	0.41	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Madhya Pradesh	0.59	0.51	0.58	0.53	0.25	0.35	0.43	0.45	0.00	0.42	0.43	0.38	0.52	0.25	0.40	0.46	6.55	0.41	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Lakshadweep	0.00	1.00	0.35	1.00	0.47	0.78	0.26	0.00	0.86	0.00	0.24	0.11	0.48	0.02	0.19	0.68	6.44	0.40	Low Level of Women Empowerment
Rajasthan	0.42	0.19	0.46	0.37	0.10	0.28	0.20	0.25	0.22	0.43	0.51	0.55	0.44	0.12	0.32	0.56	5.42	0.34	Low Level of Women Empowerment

Source: <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/FR375/FR375.pdf>

In Table 2, values related to various selected indicators of Women Empowerment are extracted from the report of the National Family Health Survey-5. From the actual values mentioned in Table 2, the dimension index values are furthermore calculated to construct an index of women empowerment.

i. Areas with High Levels of Women Empowerment

With a composite mean of the dimension index (DI) ranging from 0.60 to 0.62, three Indian states—Tamil Nadu, Goa, and Sikkim—as well as two Union Territories (UTs)—Dadra & Nagar Haveli, Daman & Diu, and Puducherry—are classified as having a high level of women’s empowerment.

Among these states, Tamil Nadu (0.62) secures the best position in terms of women empowerment as the state has the highest DI value (0.99, 0.95, and 0.91) in three indicators like the percentage of women having a bank or savings account that they use, educational attainment and percentage of women knowing a microcredit programme respectively and has also earned a good position in indicators such as percentage of women employed in the last 12 months, percentage of women earning cash, the percentage of women owing a mobile phone (Kumar and Mondal, 2024). A study by Kumari and Siotra in 2023 recognized Tamil Nadu as the top-performing state in India, performing exceptionally well in socio-cultural, educational, and economic components. This aligns with the state’s financial inclusion policies, such as the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY), and state-level initiatives to enhance women’s financial autonomy.

A study by (Kumari and Siotra, 2023) highlights that Tamil Nadu’s financial inclusion initiatives, combined with high literacy rates, significantly contribute to women’s financial empowerment. The Annual Report of the Reserve Bank of India (2022) also indicates the strong performance of Tamil Nadu in promoting financial literacy and access to banking services, particularly among women. Tamil Nadu has focused on girl-child education through initiatives like the Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya and the Free Education Scheme for Girls, which has been widely acknowledged. These efforts have resulted in significant improvements in women’s educational attainment. A study conducted by Kabeer (2005) emphasizes the link between Tamil Nadu’s educational policies and increased women’s empowerment. The state’s high DI value for women knowing a microcredit program reflects the impact of schemes like Mahalir Thittam and Self-Help Group (SHG) programmes implemented under the Tamil Nadu Corporation for Development of Women (TNCDW). Research by Biswas and Banu (2023) identifies Tamil Nadu as a leader in SHG penetration and awareness, attributing it to the state’s robust microfinance framework and active rural development programmes. The Ministry of Rural Development’s report on SHG performance highlights Tamil Nadu as one of the top-performing states, with a strong presence of microcredit initiatives for women. Tamil Nadu demonstrates a relatively high percentage of women employed compared to other states, indicating progressive participation in the labor force. This is supported by programmes aimed at women’s skill development and employment generation, such as Tamil Nadu Skill Development Corporation (TNSDC) initiatives.

According to Kumar and Mondal (2024), Tamil Nadu’s economic policies have created an environment that is conducive to women’s financial independence through cash-earning opportunities. Tamil Nadu ranks high in mobile phone ownership among women, a critical indicator of access to information and digital empowerment. This reflects the impact of the state’s digital literacy campaigns and schemes for subsidized mobile distribution to SHG members. According to this study, Goa (0.62) holds the top spot for women’s empowerment, as the state has the highest DI value (1.00) for two variables: the proportion of women who own a mobile phone and the proportion

who use their phones for financial transactions, indicating digital literacy. Indicators including the percentage of women who earn cash (among those who have worked in the past 12 months), the percentage of women who have a bank or savings account that they utilize, the percentage of women who are aware of a microcredit programme, and control over women's earnings have also given the state a strong position. Kumari and Siotra (2023) also recognized Goa as one of the most women-empowered states in India, performing exceptionally well in socio-cultural, educational, and health components. However, our analysis reveals three notable exceptions in indicators such as women owning a house alone or jointly (0.14), women owning land alone or jointly (0.05), and freedom of movement (0.27).

Despite having a high per capita income and an 88.7% literacy rate, Goa does not give women equal opportunity in the workforce, according to the Union Ministry of Labor and Employment (Patnaik, 2023). Given this, it can be claimed that Goa has the highest degree of women empowerment and, as a result, excels in four key areas: decision-making, employment, digital and financial literacy, and control over earnings. However, the state's performance in terms of women's ownership of assets is mediocre, and there are still some issues regarding freedom of movement. Various scholars have also observed a similar association in decision-making across economic, educational, and health dimensions (Kumari and Siotra, 2023; Singh et al., 2018).

Similarly, Dadra & Nagar Haveli and Daman & Diu also secured top positions in the women's empowerment index, with the highest dimension index value (1.00) in indicators such as the percentage of employed women earning more or about the same as their husbands and the percentage of women having money that they can decide how to use. This region also secures a better position in other indicators, such as the percentage of women earning cash (among those employed in the past 12 months) and mobility. Along with the other two UTs, Sikkim has made remarkable progress in women empowerment through strong literacy initiatives, financial inclusion (via SHGs), and women-led organic farming.

Government policies like 50% reservation in local bodies and targeted support for female entrepreneurs have enhanced mobility, leadership, and economic independence. Cultural openness and safety further strengthen women's active role in society. From Table 3, it is evident that states and UTs that secure a high level of women's empowerment tend to have a better position in most employment status indicators, especially for women who earn cash and have access to money and credit, which reflects the effective implementation of rural finance and literacy. However, on the contrary, these states and UTs are characterized by moderate to low performance in other domains of women empowerment, such as the decision-making power of women, ownership of assets by women, and freedom of movement.

ii. Areas with Medium Levels of Women Empowerment

Areas with a medium level of women empowerment include 13 states and Union Territories from nearly every region of India. These are Karnataka, Telangana, Andhra Pradesh, and the Andaman & Nicobar Islands from the southern region; Chandigarh, Punjab, and Ladakh from the north; Chhattisgarh from the central region; Jharkhand and Odisha from the east; Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, and Meghalaya from the northeast; and Gujarat from the western region. This group demonstrates moderate success in key indicators such as employment status, ownership of assets by women, access to credit and financial services, and educational attainment. Among them, Karnataka, Jharkhand, Chandigarh, and Punjab lead with an index value of 0.56.

The reasons behind their medium-level performance are a mix of commendable initiatives and persistent structural barriers. Karnataka performs well across most indicators due to schemes

like Udyogini and Stree Shakti promoting women's education and employment. However, deeply rooted patriarchal norms continue to hinder women's participation in household decision-making. Telangana and Andhra Pradesh have expanded self-help group movements through SERP and MEPMA, improving financial inclusion, yet limited market access and uneven implementation reduce their overall impact. In northern India, urbanization and better infrastructure have helped improve education and asset ownership among women in Chandigarh and Punjab. However, entrenched gender norms and safety concerns still restrict their full agency. Ladakh benefits from close-knit governance and a small population but remains disadvantaged due to geographical isolation and a lack of robust institutions.

In central India, Chhattisgarh has adopted initiatives like the Mahila Shakti Kendra, but widespread poverty and tribal area insecurity impede lasting outcomes. Odisha and Jharkhand have progressed through livelihood programs and forest rights in the east, though health disparities and school dropouts remain issues. The northeastern states—Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, and Meghalaya—reflect more substantial cultural gender parity yet face economic limitations and poor infrastructure. Gujarat's industrial growth and programs like Mission Mangalam support women's inclusion, but low political representation and regional inequality temper its progress. Overall, while many of these regions show improvements in education, work participation, and financial access for women, the absence of gender-sensitive governance, weak policy enforcement, and resistance to behavioural change continue to constrain their advancement beyond the medium level of empowerment.

iii. Areas with Low Levels of Women Empowerment

Sixteen out of twenty-eight Indian states—Himachal Pradesh, Bihar, Delhi, Maharashtra, Uttarakhand, Mizoram, Tripura, Nagaland, Uttar Pradesh, Kerala, Assam, West Bengal, Haryana, Jammu & Kashmir, Madhya Pradesh, and Rajasthan—along with one Union Territory, Lakshadweep, fall into the category of low women empowerment, with index values ranging from 0.46 to 0.34. Among these, Rajasthan records the lowest empowerment levels, primarily due to entrenched patriarchy, early marriages, low female literacy, and severe restrictions on women's mobility. Similarly, states like Uttar Pradesh and Bihar continue to exhibit weak outcomes despite government schemes like Beti Bachao Beti Padhao and NRLM, as women's access to education, formal employment, and financial autonomy remains limited.

In Madhya Pradesh and parts of central India, the intersection of poverty, social conservatism, and inadequate institutional outreach hinders progress. Even in states with stronger infrastructure and urbanization, such as Delhi and Maharashtra, issues like informal employment, lack of asset ownership, and public safety concerns restrict women's empowerment. In northeastern states like Mizoram and Tripura, despite cultural patrilineality, the scarcity of formal employment and economic opportunities confines women to low-income or unpaid roles.

Kerala presents a paradox: while it excels in female literacy, mobile phone ownership, and women earning an income, low asset ownership, poor mobility, and minimal control over spousal income contribute to its unexpectedly low empowerment score. In their research, several scholars have also noted that the lack of formal, high-quality positions, rising expectations of educated women in the workforce, and increasing household income are some of the reasons that contribute to unemployment among educated females in Kerala (Shekhar, 2021; Singariya and Shekhawat, 2015). Panicker (2016) and others observed that societal norms and limited formal job availability contribute to underemployment among educated women, reflecting a broader trend of structural and cultural barriers suppressing empowerment across these low-ranking states.

iv. Analysis of Various Indicators of Women Empowerment through a Correlation Matrix

The percentage of women employed in the past 12 months (W_1) is positively associated with most indicators of women’s empowerment, such as ownership of assets (land, house, mobile phones) and the literacy rate of women. However, W_1 is negatively related to other indicators, such as decision-making regarding financial aspects and household purchases, freedom of movement, and the percentage of women earning the same or more than men (Yadav et al., 2020). Employment (W_1) is positively linked to asset ownership and literacy but negatively associated with financial decision-making, mobility, and earning parity with men.

The percentage of women earning cash has a strong positive correlation with bank account usage, indicating that women who earn cash are more likely to manage their financial resources, and a negative correlation with land ownership, possibly reflecting disparities in economic empowerment based on asset ownership. Table 4 further reflects that three major indicators (control of women over women’s cash earnings, i.e., W_4 , control of women over men’s cash earnings, i.e., W_5 , and decisions related to major household purchases, i.e., W_6 , of decision-making power of women highly positively correlated with control over major financial decisions (see also Yadav et al., 2020) and positively related with the percentage of women owing a mobile phone. On the contrary, W_4 , W_5 and W_6 are highly negatively correlated with ownership of assets by women and negatively correlated with other indicators such as the use of money, percentage of women taking micro-credit loans, using mobile phones for financial transactions, mobility, literacy, etc.

Table 4: Women Empowerment: Correlations among Key Indicators

	W_1	W_2	W_3	W_4	W_5	W_6	W_7	W_8	W_9	W_{10}	W_{11}	W_{12}	W_{13}	W_{14}	W_{15}	W_{16}
W_1	1.00															
W_2	-0.12	1.00														
W_3	0.13	-0.09	1.00													
W_4	-0.43	0.23	-0.35	1.00												
W_5	-0.17	0.09	0.13	0.61	1.00											
W_6	-0.14	0.19	-0.06	0.73	0.85	1.00										
W_7	0.41	-0.16	0.30	-0.64	-0.26	-0.36	1.00									
W_8	0.31	-0.38	0.28	-0.67	-0.35	-0.47	0.88	1.00								
W_9	0.00	0.18	-0.37	0.26	0.16	0.28	-0.15	-0.27	1.00							
W_{10}	-0.07	-0.07	-0.01	-0.05	0.27	0.07	-0.08	0.06	-0.04	1.00						
W_{11}	-0.22	0.11	0.15	0.05	-0.01	-0.13	-0.09	0.07	0.09	0.39	1.00					
W_{12}	0.11	0.29	-0.04	-0.29	-0.16	-0.26	0.14	0.09	0.19	0.20	0.17	1.00				
W_{13}	0.02	0.32	-0.03	0.15	-0.20	-0.05	-0.08	-0.20	-0.22	-0.41	-0.20	0.32	1.00			
W_{14}	0.26	0.17	-0.09	-0.17	-0.35	-0.22	0.17	0.09	-0.32	-0.24	-0.40	0.29	0.71	1.00		
W_{15}	0.14	0.17	0.08	-0.17	-0.10	-0.17	0.17	0.13	0.32	-0.01	0.27	0.34	0.02	-0.09	1.00	
W_{16}	0.14	0.09	0.10	-0.16	0.05	-0.05	0.33	0.19	0.09	0.06	0.34	0.09	-0.10	-0.14	0.00	1

The decision-making indicators (W_4 , W_5 and W_6) are strongly linked to financial control and mobile ownership but are inversely related to asset ownership, financial transactions, mobility, and literacy. Freedom of movement (W_{10}) posits a weak correlation across most indicators, suggesting

that mobility may operate independently of other aspects of empowerment (see also Becker et al., 2006). On the other hand, access to money and credit has a significant positive correlation with knowledge of micro-credit loans (W_{13}) and percentage of women taking micro-credit loans (W_{14}), showing a connection between financial knowledge and access. W_{15} (mobile financial transactions) is positively related to W_{12} . A Positive correlation exists between the percentage of women using mobile phones for financial transactions and the percentage of women having bank accounts, indicating that access to bank accounts often complements the use of mobile or digital financial tools. The women's literacy rate (W_{16}) is positively correlated with most empowerment indicators, including employment (W_1) and bank account usage (W_{12}), underscoring the foundational role of education in empowerment (see also Kabeer, 2005; Mason and Smith, 2000).

The correlation matrix highlights significant relationships between various indicators of women empowerment. Employment positively influences asset ownership but does not necessarily improve control over earnings. Indicators of decision-making and asset ownership are closely associated, indicating that advancements in one area often support the other. Mobility appears to function independently, showing weaker correlations with other indicators. Financial access improves with increased earnings and literacy, with education playing a central role in enhancing multiple dimensions of empowerment. Overall, the findings underscore the interconnectedness of empowerment dimensions, emphasizing the importance of comprehensive and targeted policies.

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

Since independence, India has consistently tried to uplift its people's socio-economic status, with a special emphasis on empowering women. Despite these efforts, challenges like uneven resource distribution, limited access to services, and inconsistent policy implementation have created barriers to equitable development. This study examines women empowerment across six major domains and 16 critical indicators from the NFHS-5 dataset, aiming to capture the varied levels of empowerment across different states in India.

The analysis reveals stark regional differences in women's empowerment. Central Indian states, such as Madhya Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh, along with northern states like Himachal Pradesh, Haryana, and Uttarakhand, exhibit lower levels of empowerment. Rajasthan ranks as the least empowered state based on the Women Empowerment Index (WEI). On the other hand, states such as Goa, Tamil Nadu, and Sikkim, particularly in the southern and northeastern regions, exhibit significantly higher levels of empowerment. These states benefit from strong government initiatives in education, employment, and financial inclusion. Interestingly, the lack of empowerment is not limited to the BIMARU states. States like Assam, West Bengal, and Tripura also face significant challenges. A study by Kumari and Siotra (2023) highlighted the poor performance of the BIMARU states in developmental, social, and demographic indicators (Singh, 2023).

Smaller states, such as Goa and Sikkim, consistently outperform larger ones, like Rajasthan and Uttar Pradesh, in achieving equitable outcomes across various dimensions of women's empowerment. However, no uniform trend emerges in the economic dimension. For instance, women in Meghalaya and Chhattisgarh excel economically, while Bihar struggles. Tamil Nadu, Manipur, and Sikkim lead in the education domain, while Mizoram and Haryana lag behind. The study also highlights that while higher female literacy rates positively influence employment opportunities, asset ownership, and mobility, they do not significantly improve women's decision-making power. This underscores the need for comprehensive government investment in education, job creation, poverty reduction, and overall empowerment to boost women's workforce participation—an essential step toward

financial independence and empowerment.

An unexpected finding is Kerala's position. Despite its reputation for high female literacy, Kerala does not feature among the top fifteen states in the WEI rankings. Conversely, Chhattisgarh, often perceived as economically disadvantaged, performs notably better than Kerala on the index.

The study concludes that no state has successfully empowered women comprehensively across all dimensions due to India's diverse cultural and socio-economic landscape. Bridging these gaps requires reducing regional disparities and promoting equity. Government programs focusing on family planning and social development should prioritize economic empowerment and decision-making abilities. Women also need greater support and opportunities within their families and society to balance their roles as caregivers and active contributors. Addressing women empowerment effectively requires region-specific strategies considering local socio-economic and geo-political realities. Encouraging women participation in decision-making processes is crucial for breaking down entrenched stereotypes and promoting inclusive growth.

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